

The Predictive Role of Student Well-being, Anhedonia and Brain Fog on Mental Health among Adolescent Students

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Adolescence is a time period where adolescents experience physical, emotional and social changes. These make them vulnerable to mental health problems. There are multiple factors that affect mental health. One in seven adolescents experiences mental health conditions (WHO, 2021). The aim of the present study is to assess the influence of student well-being, anhedonia and brain fog on mental health of adolescent students. A total of 150 adolescent students took part in the study. Simple Random sampling has been employed. The research design employed is a predictive correlational research design. Standardized questionnaires like Mental Health Continuum-Short Form (MHC-SF) (Keyes, 2011), Student Subjective Well-being Questionnaire (Renshaw et al., 2015), Anhedonia Scale for Adolescents (Watson, McCabe, & Harvey, 2021), and Brain Fog Scale (Debowska, 2024) were used to assess mental health, student well-being, anhedonia and brain fog respectively. Data were analysed using Multiple Linear Regression in SPSS 27. Results emphasized that student well-being emerged as the strongest positive predictor followed by brain fog and anhedonia. This highlights that enhancing student well-being while reducing anhedonia and brain fog may strengthen adolescents' mental health.

Keywords: Mental health, student well-being, anhedonia, brain fog, adolescent students

Adolescence is a period of change comprising biological, emotional, cognitive and social aspects, leading to sensitive period of mental health changes. This is the time wherein adolescents experience important cognitive maturation, emotional reactivity and identity exploration (WHO, 2025). These can either develop resilience or vulnerability to mental health difficulties. One in seven adolescents experiences mental health conditions, such as anxiety, depression or psychosomatic distress. These can hinder academic and social functioning (UNICEF, 2022). Thus, it is essential to understand the predictors of adolescent mental health.

According to Keyes (2011), mental health is a continuum that exhibits the presence of positive functioning rather than just the absence of illness. According to this model, mental health is a spectrum ranging from flourishing (optimal functioning) to languishing (poor functioning). This holistic view combines emotional, psychological and social well-being. The positive mental health influences learning, adaptation and resilience positively (Huppert & So, 2013). As school and peer environment shape psychological outcomes, these aspects are essential for adolescents (Suldo et al., 2014). In the academic aspect, adolescents experience multiple issues that may affect their psychological well-being, including academic pressure, reduced motivation and cognitive

overload (Ahmed et al., 2023).

Student well-being is defined as the positive emotional engagement, academic efficacy, sense of belonging and satisfaction with school experiences (Renshaw et al., 2015). Students with higher well-being frequently experience stronger resilience, motivation and academic performance (Srem-Sai et al., 2025). Higher well-being is linked to better peer relationships and reduced psychological distress (Kern et al., 2015). Hence, student well-being is a crucial protective factor that improves overall mental health. Anhedonia is the inability to experience pleasure (APA, 2018). It emerged as an important risk factor for poor mental health. It is found to be associated with depressive tendencies, emotional blunting, reduced motivation and emotional disengagement from reinforcing experiences (Watson et al., 2021). Anhedonia is found to be an increasing pattern in adolescence (Yang et al., 2022). Adolescents experiencing anhedonia frequently report decreased participation in social and academic activities, resulting in poor well-being and higher vulnerability to mental distress (Pizzagalli, 2022).

Brain fog is defined as the characteristics of cognitive fatigue, mental cloudiness, impaired memory and concentration difficulties, also diminishes cognitive and emotional resources (Debowska et al., 2022). Though often overlooked, brain fog has acquired increasing attention in recent years, since it is linked to stress, digital overload and burnout among students (Ahmed et al., 2023). People with brain fog are found to experience decreased confidence in their cognitive abilities, overthinking, indecision and depressive mood (Maria et al., 2022). Continuous cognitive exhaustion can affect self-regulation, executive functioning and emotion management and thus result in poor mental health and academic performance (Orfei et al., 2022).

Although there is research evidence that highlights the independent association of these variables with mental health, limited research has explored their combined predictive effect in

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adolescents. This is needed to construct an intervention to enhance mental health through these variables.

Method

Participants

A sample of 150 adolescent students in Madurai was selected through Simple Random sampling. They are between 12-14 years of age ($M = 12.8$, $SD = .75$). This sample comprised of 80 boys and 70 girls. About 62.7% were from urban areas and 37.3% were from rural areas. Informed consent was obtained from students and their parents.

Measures

Student Subjective Well-being Questionnaire (Renshaw et al., 2015). This questionnaire consists of 16 items with four dimensions: Joy of Learning, School Connectedness, Educational Purpose, and Academic Efficacy. It is a four-point Likert scale with response options almost never, sometimes, often and almost always. Higher scores indicate greater well-being. Reliability co-efficient found to be .86

The Anhedonia scale for Adolescents (ASA) (Watson, McCabe, & Harvey, 2021). This scale comprises 14 items and three subscales- Enjoyment, Enthusiasm, and Effort. It has a four-point Likert scale with response options never, sometimes, often and always. Higher scores denote greater anhedonia. Cronbach's α was found to be .75

Brain Fog Scale (Debowska, 2024). It includes 23 items with 3 dimensions - Mental Fatigue, Impaired Cognitive Acuity, and

Confusion. This five-point Likert scale with response options never, rarely, occasionally, a lot of the time and nearly all the time. Higher scores reflect greater brain fog. The reported reliability coefficient was .71

Mental Health Continuum Short Form (MHC-SF) (Keyes, 2011). This includes 14 items. It has six-point Likert scale with response options every day, almost every day, about 2 or 3 times a week, about once a week, once or twice and never. Higher scores indicate greater positive mental health. Reliability found to be .80

Procedure

Prior permission from institution was obtained. Informed consent forms were collected from students and their parents. The students completed the questionnaires during school hours in a supervised classroom environment. They were assured of confidentiality and informed about the study's purpose. Responses were coded and analyzed using SPSS 27.

Statistical Analysis

Descriptive statistics, Pearson correlation and multiple linear regression were utilized to analyze the data.

Results

The correlation and multiple linear regression analysis revealed the results of the research. The objective is to assess the predictive role of the independent variables (student well-being, anhedonia, brain fog) on mental health.

Table 1

Pearson Correlation among Student Well-Being, Anhedonia, Brain Fog and Mental Health of Adolescent Students

Variable	n	M	SD	1	2	3	4
1. Student well-being	150	49.89	8.89	-			
2. Anhedonia	150	14.59	7.94	-0.528**	-		
3. Brain fog	150	35.16	16.24	-0.542**	0.462**	-	
4. Mental health	150	42.77	11.98	0.676**	-0.531**	-0.658**	-

Note. ** $p < .01$

In Table 1, descriptive statistics showed the following means and standard deviations: student well-being ($M = 49.89$, $SD = 8.89$), anhedonia ($M = 14.59$, $SD = 7.95$), brain fog ($M = 35.16$, $SD = 16.24$) and mental health ($M = 42.77$, $SD = 11.98$). Pearson's product moment correlation was analyzed to identify relationships among student well-being, anhedonia, brain fog and mental health. The results highlighted significant associations among the four variables. Student well-being has a positive correlation with mental health ($r = .676$, $p < .01$). On the other hand, anhedonia was associated negatively with mental health ($r = -.531$, $p < 0.01$). Likewise, brain fog has a negative correlation with mental health ($r = -.658$, $p < .01$).

Student well-being was negatively correlated with both anhedonia ($r = -.528$, $p < 0.01$) and brain fog ($r = -.542$, $p < 0.01$). Anhedonia was positively associated with brain fog ($r = .462$, $p < 0.01$).

Table 2 shows that the model is statistically significant, $F(3,146) = 66.53$, $p < .001$ and explained 59.3% of the variance in mental health

($R^2 = .593$, Adjusted $R^2 = .584$). Multiple correlation coefficient ($R = .77$) indicated the relationship among the three predictors and mental health.

Student well-being positively predicted mental health ($\beta = .394$, $p < .001$), whereas anhedonia ($\beta = .149$, $p = .026$) and brain fog ($\beta = .376$, $p < .001$) negatively predicted mental health.

Table 2

Predictors of Mental Health among Adolescent Students

Variables	Unstd. Coeff		Std. Coeff	t	Sig.
	B	SE	Beta		
Student well-being	0.531	0.094	0.394	5.640	0.001
Anhedonia	-0.224	0.100	-0.149	-2.245	0.026
Brain fog	-0.277	0.049	-0.376	-5.616	0.001

Note. $R^2 = .593$, Adjusted $R^2 = .584$, $F(3,146) = 66.53$, $p < 0.001$

Discussion

The research studied the predictive role of student well-being, anhedonia, and brain fog on the mental health of adolescent students. The findings stated that this model significantly predicted and explained 59% of mental health of adolescent students.

Research literature is consistent with the finding that student well-being has a positive predictive effect on mental health. These articles emphasize the protective and promotive role of Well-being during adolescence (Renshaw et al., 2015; Kern et al., 2015). High satisfaction, engagement and connectedness at school exhibit higher psychological and emotional functioning. School is essential in adolescents' developmental adjustment. Positive academic experiences can develop competence, self-efficacy and belonging, which are the important components of a flourishing state of mental health (Keyes, 2011; Suldo et al., 2014).

The negative relationship between anhedonia and mental health is in line with research findings. Anhedonia is conceptualized as a major symptom of depressive affect and emotional disengagement (Watson et al., 2021). Adolescents with decreased pleasure may find it difficult to be motivated in academic and social activities, which lead to decreased mental health levels. This result illustrated the importance of identifying and focusing on hedonic deficits in the form of school-based mental health programmes.

Brain fog was found to negatively predict mental health. This is consistent with research evidence that demonstrated mental fatigue and attentional issues as predictors of adolescent well-being (Debowska et al., 2022; Ahmed et al., 2023). Brain fog is related to academic pressure, excessive screen exposure and sleep disturbance, which are associated with reduced concentration and emotional regulation (Maria et al., 2022). Brain fog might result in concentration difficulty or social engagement issues, thus lead to diminished well-being (Orfei et al., 2022).

Hence, it is clear that mental health is a multi-dimensional construct predicted by behavioural, motivational and cognitive components.

Conclusion

It is evident from the research that student well-being, anhedonia and brain fog are significant predictors of mental health of adolescent students. High student well-being enhance mental health, while increased level of anhedonia and brain fog deteriorate it. The results illustrate the need for awareness programmes that focus on emotional and cognitive factors within school systems. Building well-being, emotional engagement and cognitive clarity not only increases mental health but also develops adolescents' lives holistically in academic and personal life.

Limitations of the Study

Self-reported measures have been used to study the research variables. This can lead to responder bias. The research has been conducted in a specific geographic region. This may affect generalizability to other cultures.

Implications of the Study

In theory, the results are in line with Keyes' (2011) Mental Health Continuum Model, that emphasizes the positive functioning (e.g., student well-being) and negative symptoms (e.g., anhedonia & brain

fog) exhibit combined effect over mental health outcomes. This highlighted that mental health programmes that focus on Positive Psychological resources are much needed rather than focusing on the deficit model.

Practically, these findings highlight that interventions targeting student well-being can lead to improvement in adolescent mental health. School-based Positive Psychology programmes that enhance engagement, optimism and social connectedness such as the PERMA-based Flourishing intervention (Seligman, 2011) could be exclusively effective. Hence, intervention programmes that tap and reduce anhedonia and brain fog are needed. It is recommended that teachers and counsellors should observe symptoms of anhedonia and brain fog and provide awareness about these strategies to cope with these issues.

Suggestions for Further Research

Future research can focus on physiological or behavioural indicators of cognitive functioning, combined with brain fog can yield in-depth understanding of these aspects. There arises a need to explore mediating factors like coping strategies, academic stress or sleep quality. In addition, experimental studies hold the potential to measure the effectiveness of a particular programme in enhancing mental health of adolescent students.

References

- Ahmed, T., Khan, M., & Sharma, S. (2023). Cognitive fatigue and academic stress among adolescents: Understanding brain fog in post-pandemic schooling. *Journal of Adolescent Psychology, 58*(2), 122-135.
- American Psychological Association (2018). *APA Dictionary of Psychology*. American Psychological Association. <https://dictionary.apa.org/anhedonia>
- Debowska, A., Boduszek, D., Ochman, M., Hrapkowicz, T., Gaweda, M., Pondel, A., & Horeczny, B. (2024). Brain Fog Scale (BFS): Scale development and validation. *Personality and Individual Differences, 216*, 112427.
- Huppert, F. A., & So, T. T. C. (2013). Flourishing across Europe: Application of a new conceptual framework for defining well-being. *Social Indicators Research, 110*(3), 837-861.
- Kern, M. L., Waters, L. E., Adler, A., & White, M. A. (2015). A multidimensional approach to measuring well-being in students: Application of the PERMA framework. *The Journal of Positive Psychology, 10*(3), 262-271.
- Keyes, C. L. M. (2011). Brief description of the Mental Health Continuum Short Form (MHC-SF). *Journal of Public Health Research, 2*(3), 1-11.
- Maria, L., Patel, D., & Nair, S. (2022). Cognitive fatigue and reduced clarity among adolescents: Exploring the concept of brain fog. *Clinical Psychology and Neuroscience, 9*(2), 89-101.
- Orfei, M. D., Porcari, D. E., D'Arcangelo, S., Maggi, F., Russignaga, D., & Ricciardi, E. (2022). A new look on long-COVID effects: The functional brain fog syndrome. *Journal of Clinical Medicine, 11*(19), 5529. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jcm11195529>
- Pizzagalli, D. A. (2022). Anhedonia and the brain: Integrating affective neuroscience and depression research. *Annual Review of Clinical Psychology, 18*, 215-243.
- Renshaw, T. L., Long, A. C. J., & Cook, C. R. (2015). Assessing adolescents' positive psychological functioning at school: Development and validation of the Student Subjective Well-Being Questionnaire. *School Psychology Quarterly, 30*(4), 534-552.
- Seligman, M. E. P. (2011). *Flourish: A visionary new understanding of happiness and well-being*. Free Press.
- Srem-Sai, M., Arthur, F., Salifu, I., Amoado, M., Obeng, P., Agormedah, E. K., Hagan, J. E., & Schack, T. (2025). Modelling the associations between students' academic resilience, learning motivation, self-regulated learning and academic well-being in Ghana. *Acta Psychologica, 258*, 105278. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actpsy.2025.105278>
- Suldo, S. M., Thalji, A., & Ferron, J. (2014). Longitudinal academic outcomes predicted by early adolescents' subjective well-being, psychopathology, and mental health status yielded from a dual-factor model. *The Journal of Positive Psychology, 9*(6), 463-480.
- UNICEF (2022). *The State of the World's Children 2022: Children's mental health - On my mind*. United Nations Children's Fund. <https://www.unicef.org/reports/state-worlds-children-2022>

Watson, R., McCabe, C., & Harvey, S. (2021). The Anhedonia Scale for Adolescents (ASA): A measure of reduced pleasure responsiveness. *Journal of Affective Disorders, 282*, 996-1005.

World Health Organization (2025). *Mental health of adolescents*. World Health Organization. <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/adolescent-mental-health#:~:text=Globally%2C%20one%20in%20seven%2010,lead%20fulfilling%20lives%20as%20adults>

Yang, X., Guo, Y., Harrison, P., & Liu, X. (2022). Social and general anhedonia in adolescents: Stability and associations with other symptoms. *Journal of Adolescence, 94*(3), 380-389. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jad.12029>

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